

Conference Abstract

Understanding long-term forest vegetation dynamics in response to global change using an integrated approach

Kris Verheyen ‡

‡ Ghent University, Department of Environment, Forest & Nature Lab, Gontrode, Belgium

Corresponding author: Kris Verheyen (kris.verheyen@ugent.be)

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Abstract

Forests house most of the Earth's biodiversity and deliver crucial services to society. Like other ecosystems, forests are exposed to a wide range of global changes, such as climate change, increased nitrogen deposition and land-use changes, which undermine their biodiversity and the delivery of ecosystem services. Consequently, an understanding of the effects of global change and the underlying mechanisms are crucial to prepare our forests for the uncertain future. In this talk I will illustrate how the integration of three complementary approaches, including a large network of forest understorey vegetation resurveys, a long-term multifactor global change experiment, and a novel forest understorey model, provides insight in the way multiple, interacting global change drivers lead to understorey vegetation change in temperate forests in Europe. Such insights are crucial to provide advice for forward-looking management and policy.

Presenting author

Kris Verheyen

Presented at

KEYNOTE

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.